

ANTECEDENTS FOR IMPROVING ACCEPTANCE OF MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEMS: LEARNING FROM REGIONAL GOVERNMENTS IN INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

The regional management information system is an application used by regional governments in East Java to manage their finances. This study examines the antecedents of the successful implementation of a management information system in the regional government. The research design used is quantitative research. The population is the regional information management application users. Data collection using a questionnaire in the form of google form. Sampling using a purposive method obtained 486 Regional Asset Management Board staff in East Java who filled out a complete questionnaire. Eight hypothesis testing was carried out using SmartPLS 6.0 software. The results showed that the three hypotheses are rejected, and five hypotheses are accepted. Employees who have self-efficacy in using applications benefit from using SIMDA in completing their work. The results showed that self-efficacy was the primary initial exogenous variable that affected the new information system's successful implementation. An individual feels satisfied if the use of information technology systems and increased productivity is reflected in the actual use conditions. The government can use the research results as a strategy to increase the acceptance of new technology in its environment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Advances in information technology systems have made users of information technology systems adapt according to existing developments (Kustono & Valencia, 2017). Regional governments are obliged to develop and take advantage of advances in information technology to improve the ability to manage regional finances and distribute regional financial information to the public. One form of utilization of information technology is software as a tool in regional accounting and financial systems. Therefore, a sound financial management system must manage finances accurately, timeliness, transparency, and accountability.

To have competent financial statements, human resources who implement the accounting system are essential (Kustono, 2020). Likewise, to create competent Regional Financial Reports, human resources who understand and are qualified in government accounting, regional finance, and even organizational governance are needed in government entities. It shows that the competence of human resources in government agencies affects the quality of financial statements.

A regional management information system (SIMDA) is an application used by regional governments starting from the provincial, city, or district levels to sub-districts and villages throughout Indonesia. SIMDA is an information technology-based application system created by the Financial and Development Supervisory Agency to help regional governments implement regional financial governance following applicable regulations.

Previous research has shown inconsistencies in the factors that influence SIMDA applications' acceptance in regional governments. Self-efficacy is assumed to affect usefulness. Studies conducted by Mahmoud, Ashraf, and Ra'ed (2016) showed a significant positive impact on self-efficacy and usefulness. Self-efficacy has assumed influence intention to use. Previous research showed that self-efficacy has a significant positive effect on the intention to use (Echchabi, Al-Hajri, & Nazier Tanas, 2019; Tarhini, Hone, & Liu, 2013). The other variable, complexity, is predicted to affect perceived usefulness. Hanif, Jamal, and Ahmed (2018) showed that complexity affects usefulness. Usefulness is considered to influence attitude toward using. Teo and Zhou (2014) and Wong and Mo (2019) showed that usefulness positively affects attitude toward using. However, Amer, Ahmad, and Jo (2013) stated that usefulness did not significantly affect attitude toward using. Attitude toward using has assumed influence intention to use. Intention to use is thought to influence actual usage (Alambaigi & Ahangari, 2016; Wu, Chou, Weng, & Huang, 2011).

Previous research on technology acceptance is still rarely carried out in regional government areas. As a government employee, there is no alternative but to follow the existing regulations. Other studies generally only investigate the ease of use and usefulness variables without looking for the first cause that affects the individual's internal variables. This study integrates subjective norms (self-efficacy) and external variables (complexity). The results of the study explain and predict acceptance of or inefficiency of users of a technology user.

The difference between this study and previous research lies in the object under investigation and the antecedents variables. This research was conducted at the regional government. The regional government is unique compared to private enterprises, mainly due to the civil apparatus's behavior and goals as a non-profit public entity. This research use the selected antecedent variables were complexity and self-efficacy. The aim is to obtain exogenous variables whose values can be manipulated by the strategic actions of regional government management.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Technology Acceptance

Individual acceptance of information technology is based on the perceived usefulness and ease of use. These two constructs determine the behavior of information technology acceptance. Ease of use implies a new information system is assessed as easy to apply and does not require additional physical and mental effort. Perceived usefulness is when someone thinks that using a system increases performance and improves performance.

This study aims to measure the technology acceptance model's suitability level in analyzing the acceptance of the management information system (SIMDA) in the regional governments. Based on previous research, the framework in research is as follows in figure 1.

Figure 1. Research framework

2.2 Research Hypothesis Development

Self-efficacy is defined as the level of belief that a person can perform certain behaviors. Self-efficacy means that a user has the confidence to be able to use technology systems to complete work and carry out their duties. Ease of use theory is the potential speed of a substance that can increase intention in operating an information technology. Mahmoud, Ashraf, and Ra'ed (2016) revealed a significant positive impact of self-efficacy and usefulness, supported by previous research (Al-Azawei & Lundqvist, 2015; Lee et al., 2017; Thakkar, 2018). According to Echchabi, Al-Hajri, and Nazier Tanas (2019), in their research, it shows that self-efficacy has a significant positive effect on the intention to use e-banking services. These results are also supported by Tarhini, Hone, and Liu (2013), which states that a higher self-efficacy induces a more active learning process. These findings are also in line with Gbongli, Xu, and Amedjonekou (2019) regarding self-efficacy, which significantly affects e-banking services.

H₁: Self-efficacy affects the usefulness of a management information system in the regional government.

H₂: Self-efficacy affects the perceived ease of using a management information system in the regional government.

Complexity is based on the results achieved in work and how long it takes to complete the task. The complexity level is measured by computer technology's difficulty to be understood and used by users. The complexity of a management information system at Regional government is one reason users are reluctant to use it because they are considered to spend a long time in its application. According to research conducted by Zarei, Nazari, and FarhadPoor, (2019), complexity affects usefulness. It is also supported by Igbaria and Iivari (1995) studies that give results in complexity level has a significant positive effect on usefulness.

H₃: Complexity affects the perceived usefulness of a management information system in the regional governments.

Ease of use is the potential speed of a substance that can increase the intention to use information technology. (Kustono & Valencia, 2017) states that the use of information technology can improve job performance. If users believe that it is ease to use information technology, they will use information technology to improve their performance. George Saadé, Nebebe, and Tan (2007) and Teo and Zhou (2014) explain a significant positive influence between perceived ease of use and usefulness.

H₄: Perceived ease of use affects the usefulness of a management information system in the regional government.

Perceived usefulness is considered a measure of user confidence that using information technology can improve job performance. Compared to not using information technology, work is more efficient and effective when it is done using information technology, and the results of the work are also better. SIMDA users' attitude to regional governments is driven by how much user confidence that using information systems can improve their performance. It supports previous research that stated that perceived usefulness has a significant positive effect on using (Kustono, Nanggala, & Mas'ud, 2020; Teo & Zhou, 2014; Wong & Mo, 2019).

H₅: Perceived usefulness affects the attitude toward using a management information system in the regional government.

Ease of use is defined as how users feel confident and believe that work that uses a particular technology system does not require a lot of effort or does not require any effort. TAM attitude toward using is defined as attitudes that indicate acceptance or rejection due to someone using information technology in completing their work. It is supported by previous research that found perceived ease of use affects attitude toward using (Ma, Gam and Banning, 2017; Liao *et al.*, 2018; Sakdiyah, Effendi and Kustono, 2019).

H₆: Perceived ease of use affects attitude toward using SIMDA in the regional government.

The user's attitude to the system is accepted or rejected due to a person using it to complete their work. Behavioral intention to use information technology systems can be interpreted as behavior that continuously uses information systems. Intentions and attitudes are the basis for assessing the system's acceptance. The intention is also the most critical part of the decision to accept the system or reject it. Amer, Ahmad, and Jo (2013) and Lee *et al.* (2017) argue that attitude toward using affects the intention to use.

H₇: Attitude toward using affects the intention to use SIMDA in the regional government.

The usage behavior assessment explains that there is an influence on repeated or frequent user intention in information technology systems. Someone feels satisfied if the use of information technology systems is ease to use and can increase productivity, reflected in usage behavior conditions (Brusso, 2015). Usually, in the use of information technology systems, it can be seen from the amount of time and frequency when using the information technology system. Several kinds of research found that intention to use affects actual usage (Alambaigi & Ahangari, 2016; Ramírez-Correa, Rondan-Cataluña, & Arenas-Gaitán, 2014; Wu *et al.*, 2011; Yuwana & Kustono, 2017).

H₈: Intention to use affects the usage behavior of a management information system in the regional government.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Population and Sample

A population is a group of people, events, or anything that has specific characteristics. The population is employees who use SIMDA at the regional government. The sample is a portion of the population or a selected number of members of the population. The purposive method was used for sampling. The sample is SIMDA users at the regional government. The number of samples taken was 486 SIMDA users in the regional government of the province of East Java - Indonesia.

3.2 Measurement of Variables

Variables are anything that can provide a difference or variation in a value. The variables used are divided into two categories, namely exogenous variables and endogenous variables, with the following operational definitions:

a. Exogenous Variables

Independent or exogenous variables are types of variables that explain or influence other variables.

- Complexity is measured by the difficulty of a technology system to be understood and used by users (Rogers, 1971).

- Self-efficacy is a belief that a person can perform certain behaviors (Jogiyanto, 2008).

b. Endogenous Variables

The endogenous variable is a variable that is influenced or becomes a result of an independent variable (exogenous). It is measured using Davis's instrument (1989).

- Usefulness is a measure of user belief that using information technology increases one's performance in completing work.
- Ease of use is a measure by which users believe that technology systems can be used easily and are free from problems.
- Attitude toward using is a user's attitude that shows accepting or rejecting the system's use in completing their work.
- Intention to use is a tendency as a user behavior that cannot stop using technology.
- Usage behavioral explains the actual number of SIMDA users from the start of the launch to date and the frequency of satisfaction of SIMDA users who still use the system to complete their work.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

After analyzing the data quality, the next step is to process the research variables' descriptive statistical data. The results of descriptive statistical data processing of research variables are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistic

Variables	Min	Max	Mean	Dev. Std
Usefulness	10	20	16	2.0762
Ease of Use	6	15	12	1.8002
Attitude toward Using	11	20	16	1.8377
Intention to Use	18	30	24	2.8265
Complexity	10	20	16	2.1541
Self-Efficacy	24	45	35	4.0713
Usage Behavioral	10	20	16	2.3110

Based on Table 4.1, the usefulness variable shows a mean value of 16. The lowest value for the usefulness variable is 10 (ten), and the highest value is 20. The standard deviation is 2.0762. It means that the standard deviation value is closer to the mean value, and the size of the data distribution relatively reliable.

The ease of use variable shows a mean value of 12. The lowest value of the ease of use variable is 6 (six), and the highest value is 15. The standard deviation is 1,8002. It means that the standard deviation value is closer to the mean value, and the size of the data distribution relatively reliable.

The mean value of attitude shows 16. The lowest value of the attitude toward using is 11, and the highest value is 20. The standard deviation is 1.8377. It means that the standard deviation value is closer to the mean value, and the size of the data distribution relatively reliable.

The mean value of intention is 24. The lowest value of the intention variable is 18, and the highest value is 30. The standard deviation is 2.8265. It means that the standard deviation value is closer to the mean value, and the size of the data distribution relatively reliable.

The complexity variable shows a mean value of 16. The lowest value of the variable is 10 (ten), and the highest value is 20. The standard deviation is 2.1541. It means that the standard deviation value is closer to the mean value, and the size of the data distribution relatively reliable.

The self-efficacy variable shows a mean value of 35. The lowest value for the self-efficacy variable is 24, and the highest value is 45. The standard deviation is 4.0713. It means that the standard deviation value is closer to the mean value, and the size of the data distribution relatively reliable.

The usage behavior variable shows a mean value of 16. The lowest value of the usage behavior variable is 10, and the highest value is 20. The standard deviation is 2.3110. It means that the standard deviation value is closer to the mean value, and the size of the data distribution relatively reliable.

4.1.1 Convergent Validity

The outer loading or loading factor value is used to test the convergent validity. Outer loading values between 0.5 - 0.6 are considered sufficient to meet the convergent validity requirements. The research data shows no variable indicator whose outer loading value is below 0.5, so all indicators are declared valid.

4.1.2 Discriminant Validity

The discriminant validity test uses the cross-loading value. Indicators that meet discriminant validity have the most significant cross-loading indicator value Compared to other variables.

The test results in table 2 show that each research variable's indicator has a cross-loading value > R table. It can be concluded that the research variables met the criteria for discriminant validity.

Tabel 2. Composite Reliability

Variable	Cross Loading Value	R _{table}	Decision
Usage behavior	0.798	0.195	Valid
Attitude toward Using	0.733	0.195	Valid
Intention to Use	0.822	0.195	Valid
Complexity	0.733	0.195	Valid
Perceived Ease of Use	0.912	0.195	Valid
Perceived Usefulness	0.872	0.195	Valid
Self-Efficacy	0.718	0.195	Valid

4.1.3 Composite Reliability

Composite reliability is a test of the reliability value of a variable indicator. A variable meets the reliability of the composite if it has a composite reliability value > 0.6.

Tabel 3. Composite Reliability

Variables	Composite Reliability
Usage behavior	0.873
Attitude toward Using	0.849
Intention to Use	0.733
Complexity	0.793
Perceived Ease of Use	0.861
Perceived Usefulness	0.793
Self-Efficacy	0.843

Based on the table 3, the composite reliability value of all research variables is greater than 0.6. Each variable meets the composite reliability criteria. In other words, all variables have a high level of reliability.

4.1.4 Cronbach Alpha

The reliability test results showed that the Cronbach alpha value was greater than 0.7. The results in table 4 indicate that each research variable has met the requirements for the Cronbach alpha value. It shows that all variables are reliable and can be used for further analysis.

Tabel 4. Cronbach Alpha

Variables	Cronbach alpha
Usage behavior	0.803
Attitude toward Using	0.791
Intention to Use	0.801
Complexity	0.786
Perceived Ease of Use	0.757
Perceived Usefulness	0.786
Self-Efficacy	0.787

4.1.5 Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing was carried out by looking at the T-Statistics value and the P-Values value. The research hypothesis can be accepted if the P-Values value is <0.05. From the results of the research hypothesis testing model using SmartPLS 6.0, as shown above, then can be seen that the direct effect or indirect effect of the relationship between the variables. Table 1 shows the direct effect of the relationship between variables.

Table 5. Results of Interrelationship Variables

Hypothesis	Path Coefficients	P-value	Result
H1	Self-Efficacy → Usefulness	0.422	0.000**
H2	Self-Efficacy → Intention to Use	0.731	0.000**
H3	Complexity → Usefulness	0.822	0.648
H4	Ease of Use → Usefulness	0.517	0.000**
H5	Usefulness → Attitude Toward Using	-0.356	0.225
H6	Ease of Use → Attitude Toward Using	0.580	0.057
H7	Attitude toward Using → Intention to Use	0.402	0.000**
H8	Intention to Use → Usage behavior	0.822	0.000**

Based on testing the direct effect of Figure 4.2 and Table 4.7 above, it can be seen that:

- a. The path coefficient value from self-efficacy to usefulness is $\beta = 0.422$, which is positive. The p-value of 0.000 is significant because the p-value is less than 0.05. Hypothesis 1 states that self-efficacy affects the usefulness of SIMDA on regional government is accepted. The path coefficient value of self-efficacy on the intention to use is $\beta = 0.731$. The p-value of 0.000 is significant because the p-value is less than 0.05. Hypothesis 2 states that self-efficacy has an effect on the intention to use SIMDA regional government is accepted.
- b. The path coefficient value of complexity to usefulness is $\beta = 0.822$. The p-value of 0.648 is not significant because the p-value is more than 0.05. Hypothesis 3 that complexity affects the perception of SIMDA regional government's usefulness is rejected.
- c. The path coefficient value from the ease of use to usefulness is $\beta = 0.517$. The p-value of 0.000 is significant because the p-value is less than 0.05. Hypothesis 4 states that ease of use affects the usefulness of SIMDA on regional government accepted.
- d. The path coefficient value from usefulness to attitude toward using is $\beta = -0.356$, which is negative. The p-value of 0.225, this result is not significant because the p-value is more than 0.05. Hypothesis 5 states that usefulness affects the attitude of using the SIMDA system the regional government is rejected.
- e. The path coefficient value of the ease of use on usage attitudes is $\beta = 0.580$. The p-value of 0.057, this result is not significant because the p-value is more than 0.05. Hypothesis 6, which states ease of use affects the SIMDA regional government's attitude, is rejected.
- f. The path coefficient value of attitude toward using to intention to use is $\beta = 0.402$. The p-value of 0.000 is significant because the p-value is less than 0.05. Hypothesis 7 that state attitude toward using affects the perception of intention to use SIMDA regional government is accepted.
- g. The path coefficient value of intention to use to usage behavior is $\beta = 0.822$. The p-value of 0.000 is significant because the p-value is less than 0.05. Hypothesis 8 states that intention to use an effect on the usage behavior of SIMDA of regional government is accepted.

4.2 Discussion

4.2.1 Self-Efficacy, Usefulness, and Intention to Use

Hypothesis test results show that self-efficacy affects usefulness and intention to use it by looking at the significance level of 0.000. The effect demonstrated by the regression coefficient is positive, meaning that the higher the self-efficacy, the usefulness, and the intention to use it increase. Hypotheses 1 and 2 are accepted. Employees who feel they can use SIMDA get benefits from using SIMDA in completing their work. On the other hand, if the employees' ability is low in using SIMDA, then the perceived benefits of using SIMDA will also be below. The relationship between the self-efficacy variable and the intention to use shows a positive effect. When regional government employees feel they can use SIMDA, the intention

to use the SIMDA also increases. On the other hand, regional government employees use low SIMDA levels, reducing their intention to use the system.

Self-efficacy is defined as the level of confidence that a person can perform certain behaviors. Nagy (2018) self-efficacy means that a user has the confidence to use technological systems to complete work and perform tasks. Ease of use is the potential speed of a substance that can increase the intention to use information technology. Mahmoud, Ashraf, and Ra'ed (2016) revealed a significant positive impact of self-efficacy and usefulness in their research. According to Echchabi et al. (2019), in their research, it shows that self-efficacy has a significant positive effect on the intention to use e-banking services. These results are also supported by Tarhini, Hone, and Liu (2013), which states that higher self-efficacy induces a more active learning process.

4.2.2 Complexity and Usefulness

Hypothesis test results show that complexity does not affect usefulness by looking at the significance level of 0.822. The higher the complexity, the usefulness does not change. Hypothesis 3 is rejected. There is only one application in the regional government, namely SIMDA, used for regional financial management, from budgeting to financial reports preparation. Therefore, SIMDA users still have to use the system to complete their work even though the complexity level of SIMDA is high or low.

Complexity measurement is based on the results achieved in work and how long it takes to complete it. The complexity level is measured by computer technology's difficulty to be understood and used by users. The complexity of SIMDA at the Regional government is one reason users are reluctant to use it because they are considered to spend a long time in its application.

This study's results are not in line with Zarei, Nazari, and FarhadPoor (2019) research, where complexity affects usefulness. The study also supports the analysis of Hanif, Jamal, and Ahmed (2018). They confirmed the complexity level has a significant positive effect on usefulness.

4.2.3 Ease of Use and Usefulness

Hypothesis test results show that ease of use affects usefulness by looking at its significance level of 0.000. The effect demonstrated by the regression coefficient is positive, meaning that the higher the ease of use, the higher the usefulness. Hypothesis 4 is accepted. It can be influenced by the length of time that regional government employees use SIMDA, where SIMDA has been used from 2008 to the present, which results in users perceiving that SIMDA is ease to use because they already know the usefulness of the system.

Ease of use can increase intention to use information technology. The use of information technology can improve job performance. If users believe that it is ease to use information technology, they will use information technology to improve their performance. Some

previous research (George Saadé, Nebebe, and Tan, 2007; Teo and Zhou, 2014) explained a significant positive influence between perceived ease of use and usefulness.

4.2.4 Usefulness and Attitude toward Using

Hypothesis test results show that the usefulness of SIMDA does not affect attitude toward using by looking at the significance level of 0.225, meaning that the higher the usefulness, the attitude toward using does not change. Hypothesis 5 is rejected. SIMDA has long been used in the regional government for approximately 12 years, makes users familiar with and already know the usefulness of SIMDA. Thus, it prevents users from experiencing an increase in quality, effectiveness, and efficiency in completing their work.

Perceived usefulness is considered a measure of user confidence that using information technology can improve job performance. Compared to not using information technology, work is more efficient and effective when it is done using information technology, and the results of the work are also better. SIMDA users' attitude to regional governments is driven by how much user confidence that using information systems can improve their performance. This study's results are not in line with previous research (Chen, Li, and Li, 2011; Olushola and Abiola, 2017; Wong and Mo, 2019). They stated that perceived usefulness has a significant positive effect on attitude toward using.

4.2.5 Ease of Use on Attitude toward Using SIMDA

The hypothesis test results show that ease of use does not affect usage attitudes by looking at the significance level of 0.057, meaning that the higher the ease of use, the attitude toward using does not change. Hypothesis 6 is rejected. It happens because the government has been obliged to use SIMDA to manage regional finances. Thus, most SIMDA users are not yet aware of the system's clarity of purpose and convenience. Therefore, regional government employees often experience difficulties in completing their work correctly and on time.

Ease of use is a measure of how users feel confident and believe that work that uses a particular technology system does not require a lot of effort or does not require any effort. Attitudes toward using are defined as attitudes that indicate acceptance or rejection due to someone using information technology to complete their work. Chen, Li, and Li (2011), Hussein (2017), and Ma, Gam and Banning (2017) argued that perceived ease of use affects attitude toward using.

4.2.6 Attitudes and the Intention to Use

Hypothesis test results show that attitude toward using affects the intention to use by looking at the significance level of 0.000. The effect demonstrated by the regression coefficient is positive, meaning that the higher the attitude toward using, the higher the intention to use it. Hypothesis 7 is accepted. It is because there is a link between behavior and one's attitude towards an object. SIMDA is the only system used to manage regional government finances so that all provincial government employees are required to use SIMDA. It makes SIMDA users

at Regional governments have received and used it for approximately 12 years to date. Thus, users have intended to implement SIMDA in their daily activities to complete their work.

The user's attitude to the system is accepted or rejected due to a person using the system to complete their work. Intention to use information technology systems can be defined as behavior that tends to use information systems continuously. Intentions and attitudes are the basis for assessing the system's acceptance. The intention is also an essential part of the decision to accept the system or reject it. It is supported by Mohammadi and Isanejad (2018). They found attitude toward using affects the intention to use.

4.2.7 Intention to Use and Usage Behavior

Hypothesis test results indicate that the intention to use affects usage behavior by looking at the significance level of 0.000. The effect shown by the regression coefficient is positive, meaning that the higher the intention to use it, the more its use will increase. Hypothesis 8 is accepted. It is because SIMDA users at Regional governments are intentioned in using SIMDA. After all, it is more effective and efficient than the previous system. It makes current SIMDA users at Regional governments use the system for approximately 12 years to complete a day's workday.

The usage behavior assessment explains that there is an influence on repeated or frequent user intention in information technology systems. Someone feels satisfied if the use of information technology systems is ease to use and can increase productivity, reflected in the actual usage (Wida et al., 2016). Usually, in the use of information technology systems, it can be seen from the amount of time and frequency when using the information technology system. It is supported by some research that concluded that intention to use affects actual usage (Ramírez-Correa, Rondan-Cataluña, and Arenas-Gaitán, 2014; Alambaigi and Ahangari, 2016; Liao et al., 2018).

5. CONCLUSION

This study integrates subjective norms (self-efficacy) and external variables (complexity). The results of the research explain and predict acceptance of or inefficiency of users of a technology user. It can be concluded that the following matters. The results showed that self-efficacy affected perceived usefulness and behavioral intention to use, perceived ease of use involved perceived usefulness, attitudes towards use impacted behavioral intention to use, and behavioral intention to use affected actual system usage. Other hypotheses have failed to prove. Complexity does not affect perceived usefulness, and perceived usefulness has no impact on attitudes towards use. Also, perceived ease of use does not affect attitudes towards use.

The successful implementation of information systems is caused by a series of causal relationships between variables. Self-efficacy is the first culprit in this model. Strengthening the efficacy and perceived ease of use of users increases the chances of successfully implementing new information systems.

5.1 Limitation

This study contains notable limitations. Respondents are mandatory employees who use management information systems. Doing careful is needed to interpret belief values, complexity, and usage behavior. Due to these constraints, necessary must be taken in generalizing and confirming theories. Second, the distribution of online questionnaires provided the coverage of coverage during the Covid pandemic, but the content validity test process has not been carried out optimally. Third, not all variables that may affect the successful implementation of management information systems are considered in this study.

5.2 Future Research Suggestion

Testing the non-mandatory management information system model can provide better conclusion validation. Future research needs to be carried out by considering the respondents' abilities and literacy so that conclusions can be more comprehensive.

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